

The pursuit of “useless knowledge”

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August 13, 2024

[FEATURE]

It is not always obvious for even well-trained researchers to appreciate their peer’s scientific pursuits. In many cases, research results obtained from strenuous work processes could even be regarded as “useless knowledge”.

Only in very few places on this planet had the notion of useless knowledge been respected and sought after. That’s the famous IAS of Princeton University powered by the conception of the usefulness of useless knowledge of Abraham Flexner [1]. That’s why brilliant scientists such as Albert Einstein, Kurt Godel, and John von Neumann were among its first recruited members.

Illustration. Early fruits of Cleistocalyx Operculatus.

Our team has for many years now gone through various research problems. Still, it is difficult for even experienced and highly accomplished researchers to identify the type of IAS “useless knowledge” problems. But we never stopped trying.

Our latest try has led to the informational entropy-based definition of value. At first, it sounded weird for one to ponder the long-existing notion of value, which is used on a daily basis by everybody on Earth. In short, kind of... useless. But gradually, we have come to an understanding that the very familiarity of the word “value” has long obscured our question of its nature.

So, a bit about this newly minted definition is here for your perusal [2].

References

[1] Flexner A. (2017). *The usefulness of useless knowledge*. Princeton University Press. <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9781400884629/html>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://books.google.com/books/about?id=vy4ZEQAAQBAJ>

